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* **Corresponding author.**elia.ahidi@out.ac.tz**Funding:** None**Competing Interests:** None

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A Multitask Pretrained Language Model for Holistic Quality Evaluation of Curriculum and Examinations in Higher Education

Elia Elisante Lukwaro^{1,2*}, Rogers Bhalalusesa¹, Khamisi Kalegele¹, Devotha Nyambo²

¹ The Open University of Tanzania (OUT), Dar es salaam, Tanzania

² The Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST), Arusha, Tanzania

Abstract

Objectives: This study aims to identify and validate quality criteria for curriculum and examinations in Tanzanian higher education, and to develop a multitask pretrained language model that holistically assesses multiple quality dimensions simultaneously using enhanced Natural Language Processing (NLP). **Method:** A mixed-methods design was employed. Qualitative data were collected via semi-structured interviews with quality assurance personnel from 10 of 13 identified Tanzanian universities and the Tanzania Commission for Universities (TCU). Thematic analysis identified quality dimensions and indicators. Computationally, the all-MiniLM-L12-v2 (SBERT) model was fine-tuned in two phases: Phase 1 used 104,000 contrastive sentence pairs from computer science textbooks and open educational resources (OER); Phase 2 trained task-specific heads on 6,636 labelled sentences for Bloom's Taxonomy classification, learning-outcome coherence detection, and industry-skills relevance matching. **Findings:** The fine-tuned multitask model achieved a test accuracy of 97.87%, an F1 score of 97.93%, and a recall of 99.65%, outperforming prior NLP approaches on comparable educational quality tasks. The SBERT + SpaCy combined approach yielded a contextual similarity score of 0.6895 versus 0.4860 for plain SBERT, confirming enhanced deep contextual comprehension. The model demonstrated robust performance in evaluating three quality dimensions: cognitive-level alignment with Bloom's Taxonomy, coherence between learning outcomes and instructional methods, and relevance of learning outcomes to industry skill standards (ISCO). **Novelty:** This study introduces a novel multitask PLM framework that simultaneously evaluates interrelated quality dimensions of curriculum and examinations, addressing the fragmented evaluation approaches prevalent in existing literature. The integration of SpaCy-based Named Entity Recognition (NER) with SBERT embeddings, combined with a chapter-level contrastive fine-tuning strategy, yields richer contextual representations deployable in resource-constrained environments.

Keywords: Quality of education; NLP; Pretrained Language Models; Multitask Learning; Curriculum; Examinations; Bloom's Taxonomy; Higher Education

1 Introduction

Determining education quality is inherently multifaceted, as different stakeholders governments, employers, academics, students, and society conceptualize it differently^{(1), (2)}. Most higher education institutions globally evaluate quality through programs/curriculum, assessments, admission systems, and other resources⁽³⁾. The resulting complexity is compounded by constantly changing market-demanded skills, the imperative to align higher education offerings with industry needs, and the requirement for coherent learning outcomes linking education to both industry and society⁽⁴⁾.

The emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) has significantly enhanced NLP contextual comprehension^{(5), (6)}. However, for domain-specific applications, Pretrained Language Models (PLMs) are more appropriate, as they reduce the risk of misinformation and improve auditability a critical consideration for regulatory bodies⁽⁷⁾. Unlike opaque LLMs functioning as "black boxes"⁽⁸⁾, PLMs such as all-MiniLM-L12-v2 offer relative transparency through modular task-head designs, enabling interpretable classification outputs required for regulatory compliance.

A significant challenge persists in extracting nuanced curricular constructs due to the lack of standardised curricular ontologies and pedagogically grounded reasoning⁽⁹⁾. Existing approaches evaluate quality dimensions in a fragmented manner, treating coherence, relevance, and cognitive-level alignment as isolated tasks. The quality of education comprises interconnected pillars dimensions, indicators, and metrics that collectively determine holistic quality^{(2), (10)}. PLMs offer the capacity to enable scalable, context-aware assessments across all these pillars.

There is a notable gap in empirical studies from developing countries using NLP and PLMs to benchmark curriculum and examination quality against local regulatory and labour-market standards. Assessing curricula against labour market needs ensures graduates acquire necessary skills⁽¹¹⁾. The curriculum serves as the primary interface between students, teachers, and institutions, while examinations act as indicators of cognitive development and learning outcomes. This study addresses these gaps by proposing a fine-tuned multitask PLM model that simultaneously evaluates quality dimensions, observable indicators, and measurable metrics for curriculum and examinations in Tanzanian higher education.

The study is guided by three research questions: (RQ1) What quality dimensions, indicators, and metrics are relevant for evaluating curriculum and examinations in Tanzanian higher education? (RQ2) Can a fine-tuned multitask PLM simultaneously evaluate these dimensions with acceptable performance? (RQ3) How does the combined SBERT and SpaCy approach improve contextual comprehension over plain SBERT?

Recent literature confirms the broad application of NLP in adaptive learning, intelligent tutoring, and automated assessment^{(12), (13)}, while PLMs have demonstrated superiority in domain-specific scoring tasks over traditional methods^{(14), (15)}. However, most studies prioritise practical applications over domain-specific challenges, contextual understanding, and the nuanced quality of educational content^{(16), (17)}. Furthermore, the lack of clear procedures for feature extraction and alignment of curriculum features with quality outcomes limits the utility of existing frameworks⁽¹¹⁾.

This study proposes a novel framework that bridges curriculum quality evaluation with NLP-driven automation. The main contributions of this work are as follows: (i) integration of qualitative data from Tanzanian universities to derive locally contextualised quality criteria for curriculum and examination evaluation; (ii) a two-phase PLM fine-tuning strategy leveraging SpaCy Named Entity Recognition (NER) for richer, linguistically grounded embeddings; (iii) a deployable multitask model that simultaneously evaluates multiple interrelated quality dimensions, outperforming existing single-task NLP approaches while remaining resource-efficient for developing-country contexts; and (iv) empirical validation demonstrating that the combined SBERT and SpaCy approach yields a 41.9% relative improvement in contextual comprehension over plain SBERT. The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology, including data collection, model architecture, and fine-tuning procedures. Section 3 reports the experimental results and discussion. Section 4 concludes the paper with limitations and directions for future research.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data and Methods

This study employs a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and computational methods. Qualitative data collection involved semi-structured interviews with quality assurance personnel from 10 of 13 identified Tanzanian universities (drawn from the TCU guidebook for the 2022–23 academic year) and 2 personnel from the Tanzania Commission for Universities (TCU). Convenience sampling was employed for willing respondents⁽¹⁸⁾. Computational methods involved developing and fine-tuning the all-MiniLM-L12-v2 SBERT model. Benchmarking indicators were selected based on high predictive power, regular stakeholder requirement, meaningfulness, and appropriateness for benchmarking⁽¹⁹⁾.

2.2 Data Collection

Interviews were conducted in English and Swahili with bias-prevention protocols. Interview data were summarised into 10-word files per university and imported into NVivo for thematic analysis. Emerging themes included country education philosophy, learning outcomes, relevance, coherence and consistency, equity and inclusion. Computational data sources included 16 computer science textbooks, job skills standards from the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO)/ESCO, examination questions, learning outcomes from university websites and OER repositories.

2.3 Qualitative Data Analysis and Emerging Themes

Figure 1 illustrates the emerging themes from the university interviews, representing the analytical thread that informed quality indicator identification.

Fig 1. Emerging Themes from University Interviews

Interview responses highlighted: (i) national education philosophy — alignment of syllabi and assessments with self-reliance principles and global competitiveness; (ii) learning outcomes — integration of workplace-relevant skills; (iii) flexibility and relevance — adaptability to changing environments; (iv) coherence and consistency — horizontal and vertical interconnection of course topics; and (v) equity and inclusion — tailoring to sociocultural diversity. A quality assurance guide manual and literature review subsequently validated these findings^{(20), (21), (22)}.

2.4 Limitations of the Data

Training data is concentrated within computer science disciplines from Tanzanian universities, which may constrain immediate generalisability to other disciplines (medicine, law, engineering). Additionally, qualitative data from 10 of 13 universities may introduce selection bias. Open Educational Resources (OER) used in fine-tuning may not represent the full vocabulary of all

Tanzanian curricula. Future work should extend to humanities, health sciences, and engineering curricula across East African contexts.

2.5 Multitask Model Architecture

The model architecture comprises a shared SBERT encoder (all-MiniLM-L12-v2) as the backbone, augmented by multiple independently trained task-specific classification heads. The all-MiniLM-L12-v2 model features 12 transformer layers and 384-dimensional embeddings, effectively balancing semantic complexity and computational efficiency⁽²³⁾. Its modular task-head design offers interpretable classification outputs for example, Bloom’s cognitive level labels or coherence scores enabling educational stakeholders and regulatory bodies to trace evaluation criteria, addressing the auditability gap identified in prior work⁽⁸⁾.

Figure 2 illustrates the pipeline architecture: the pretrained model x_0 is fine-tuned to produce base model x_1 , which then anchors task-specific heads x_a (Bloom’s Taxonomy classification), x_b (coherence detection), and x_n (skills relevance).

Fig 2. Multitask Pipeline Architecture

2.6 Dataset Preparation

The dataset encompasses 16 computer science course books (database, network, Java, Python, C++ programming, algorithms, systems analysis, software testing, game development, GIS, machine learning, information management systems, HCI, operating systems, web and multimedia development), job skills (ISCO), interview transcripts, examination questions, learning outcomes, and unrestricted OER.

2.7 Data Preprocessing and Feature Extraction

Raw data was extracted using PyPDF2 and docx libraries. SpaCy (en_core_web_sm) was used for dependency parsing to identify action verbs, direct objects, and contextual elements — yielding verb+object+context (VOC) chunks. This novelty approach enhances the base model by extracting semantically rich, linguistically constrained textual units, improving fine-tuning quality. The combination of SpaCy’s NER capability, action verb extraction, and multitask learning architecture pushes beyond standard text analysis boundaries⁽²⁴⁾.

2.8 Task Formulation and Dataset

Table 1 summarises the data sources and sample counts across two fine-tuning phases.

Phase 1 fine-tuned the encoder using 104,000 contrastive sentence pairs via SoftmaxLoss, capturing domain-specific semantic nuances of computer science. Phase 2 trained task-specific heads on an expanded dataset of 6,636 labelled samples. Semantic-Guided Expansion (SGE) was applied: cosine similarity between Bloom questions, learning outcomes, and skills was computed, and high-similarity matches generated new training samples while preserving original task labels. This expanded the dataset from 4,530 to 6,636 labelled samples⁽²⁵⁾.

Table 1. Data Source and Sentences Generated

Source	Description	Role in Model	Sample Count
Books	Sentence-level extraction from CS textbooks; linguistically constrained semantic pair mining	Phase 1 (contrastive fine-tuning)	Used in 104,000 pairs
Examinations (Bloom's Taxonomy)	Sentence-level exam questions labelled with Bloom's cognitive levels	Phase 1 (semantic grounding), Phase 2 (Bloom classification)	3,121 (original), 4,174 (after expansion)
Learning Outcomes	Sentence-level learning outcomes labelled for coherence	Phase 1 (semantic grounding), Phase 2 (coherence classification)	1,409 (original), 2,462 (after expansion)
Skills (ISCO)	Sentence-level skill statements extracted from ISCO skills document	Phase 1 (semantic grounding), Phase 2 (semantic expansion only)	597
Phase-1 Training Pairs	Linguistically filtered positive/negative sentence pairs (balanced)	Phase 1 training	104,000 (52k positive, 52k negative)
Phase-2 Training Samples	Sentence-level labelled samples after semantic-guided expansion	Phase 2 multitask training	6,636 total

2.9 Tokenization and Novel Attention Mechanism

The fine-tuning process involves five tokenization phases: (1) intelligent VOC chunking via SpaCy; (2) WordPiece/BPE tokenization by SBERT's internal tokenizer; (3) self-attention processing with anchor tokens [VERB], [OBJ], [CTX] guiding attention maps; (4) pooling of contextual embeddings into fixed-size vectors; and (5) task-specific heads leveraging these dense embeddings for downstream classification. This mechanism significantly preserves contextual and semantic meanings across extracted sentences.

2.10 Finetuning Process and Hyperparameters

The fine-tuning process adjusted weights using GradNorm strategies⁽²⁶⁾ to balance task-specific loss functions. Hyperparameter grid search explored epochs (10, 15, 20, 25), batch sizes (16, 32, 64, 128), learning rates (0.01, 0.001, 0.0001, 0.00001), and dropout rates (0.2–0.5). The optimal configuration — epochs 20, batch size 16, learning rate 0.01, dropout 0.2 — was selected based on validation performance across more than 800 training experiments.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Base Model Fine-Tuning Performance

Figure 3 presents the training and validation dynamics of the base model fine-tuning. The graphs confirm strong model performance with no evidence of overfitting. Both training and validation metrics improved consistently across epochs.

Table 2 summarises the performance evaluation of the base model fine-tuning.

The balanced precision (0.9740) versus recall (0.9813) confirms that the model accurately identifies relevant data while maintaining a low false-negative rate. The decreasing training loss indicates effective learning, and the high F1 improvement confirms robust tabilizesion.

3.2 Multitask Model Performance

Figure 4 shows the training dynamics of the multitask fine-tuning approach. The loss gradually decreases and stabilizes in later epochs, with training and validation accuracy improving steadily. The precision-recall curves and F1 scores are stable across epochs, assuring low overfitting risk.

Table 3 presents training and validation metrics across epochs and final test evaluation.

The train loss decreased from 0.3260 (Epoch 1) to 0.0744 (Epoch 20), and train accuracy increased from 0.8695 to 0.9767, confirming effective learning. Validation accuracy improved from 0.9037 to 0.9697, indicating good generalisation. The final test evaluation recorded Accuracy: 97.87%, F1: 97.93%, Precision: 96.27%, Recall: 99.65% — confirming the model's capability to comprehend contextual and semantic relationships with no overfitting.

Fig 3. Base Model Training Results

Table 2. Performance Evaluation Summary — Base Model

Training Insight	Attributes	Value	Observation
Finetuning Setup	Epochs	20	Best performance at epoch 15–19
	Batch Size	16	Balanced with environment
	Learning Rate	0.01	Rapid stable converging
	Dropout Rate	0.2	Prevent overfitting
Final Test Evaluation	Train Accuracy	0.9733	Sufficient learning
	Validation Accuracy	0.9768	Close to training, no overfitting
	Train Loss	0.0770	Smooth and consistently decreasing
	F1 Score	0.9776	High balance between precision and recall
	Precision	0.9740	Slightly lower than recall, still strong
	Recall	0.9813	Very high, few false negatives
Training Trend	Overall Observation	Excellent convergence	No overfitting, all metrics consistently high

Table 3. Training Metrics for Multitask Model

Metric	Epoch 1	Epoch 6	Epoch 15	Epoch 20	Final Test
Train Loss	0.3260	0.1168	0.0776	0.0744	–
Train Accuracy	0.8695	0.9622	0.9733	0.9767	–
Validation Accuracy	0.9037	0.9626	0.9661	0.9697	–
Validation Precision	0.9109	0.9418	0.9514	0.9613	–
Validation Recall	0.9892	0.9857	0.9821	0.9785	–
Validation F1 Score	0.9109	0.9632	0.9665	0.9698	–
Test Accuracy	–	–	–	–	0.9787
Test F1 Score	–	–	–	–	0.9793
Test Precision	–	–	–	–	0.9627
Test Recall	–	–	–	–	0.9965

Fig 4. Multitask Heads Fine-Tuned Training Dynamics

3.3 Deep Contextual Comprehension Verification

An experiment validated the model using an employment advertisement from the National Identification Authority of Tanzania (“Mamlaka ya Vitambulisho vya Taifa”) for a Data Administrator position. The model assessed the posted skills’ compliance with learning outcomes from Database II courses extracted from Curriculum C.

Fig 5. Advert for Database Administrator Post vs. Learning Outcomes from Curriculum

Plain SBERT achieved a similarity score of 0.4860, while SBERT + SpaCy (NER + verbs + objects) achieved 0.6895 — a 41.9% relative improvement — confirming substantially enhanced contextual comprehension. Figure 6 and 7 display bipartite graphs comparing contextual alignment under both approaches.

3.4 Comparative Analysis with Existing Literature

Table 4 presents a performance and architectural comparison of this work with related studies.

This study surpasses the F1 score of Vo et al. (2022) (76.18%) and the accuracy of Das et al. (2020) (89%) while addressing a broader range of quality dimensions. Direct comparison with Gul et al. (2025) and Zhang et al. (2024) is not feasible due to different problem domains and datasets. However, this study uniquely provides a simultaneous solution for coherence checking, Bloom’s Taxonomy classification, and skills relevance assessment of all vital dimensions for holistic quality evaluation. The all-

Fig 6. Conceptual Comprehension: Integrated SBERT and SpaCy Features

Table 4. Performance and Architectural Comparison with Existing Literature

Ref-er-ences	Performance	Key Contributions
(4)	CSIT-NER F1: 76.18%; Hybrid CSIT-CRS Recall: 97.5%	Tailored NER model for CS/IT; extracts skills, provides career path and identifies demand skills
(27)	Aspect Accuracy: 96.4%; Sentiment Accuracy: 98.7%	Selective paraphrasing with nuance control enhances ABSA training data, preserving sentiment and diversity
(28)	Text Chunking + PoS: 98.45%; PoS + SBD: 97.79%; SBD + PoS: 87.48%	Novel multitask framework sharing information between tasks; improves learning stability across language tasks
(29)	Labelled LDA: 83%; BERT-based: 89%	Addresses Bloom's Taxonomy ambiguity; classifies cognitive levels including WH questions
(30)	QuaRel: 78.99%; OPENBOOKQA: 65.55%	MARIO optimizes functions with small models, outperforming others in question-answering tasks
(31)	NB F1: 0.81; KNN: 0.75	ML classifiers framework to classify questions per cognitive level
This work	F1: 97.93%; Recall: 99.65%; Accuracy: 97.87%	Novel multitask model with shared SentenceTransformer encoder; evaluates curriculum and examination quality dimensions (coherence, relevance, Bloom's level) simultaneously

Fig 7. Conceptual Comprehension: Plain SBERT

MiniLM-L12-v2 architecture differentiates this work from models relying on higher-computation PLMs (BERT, RoBERTa, XLNet), remaining deployable in resource-constrained environments.

4 Conclusion

This study presented a novel multitask pretrained language model framework for the holistic evaluation of curriculum and examination quality in Tanzanian higher education. The fine-tuned all-MiniLM-L12-v2 model achieved 97.87% accuracy, 97.93% F1, and 99.65% recall, outperforming existing NLP approaches on comparable educational quality tasks. The integration of SpaCy NER with SBERT embeddings improved contextual comprehension by 41.9% over plain SBERT, while the two-phase contrastive fine-tuning strategy yielded robust, domain-specific embeddings without overfitting.

The framework addresses a critical gap in the literature by simultaneously evaluating multiple interrelated quality dimensions cognitive-level alignment with Bloom’s Taxonomy, coherence of learning outcomes with instructional methods, and relevance to industry skill standards rather than treating these dimensions in isolation. The model is deployable in resource-constrained developing-country contexts and provides actionable quality assurance insights for regulatory bodies such as the TCU. From a practical standpoint, the framework offers university quality assurance units an automated, scalable tool to benchmark curricula against national and international standards, reducing reliance on time-intensive manual peer-review processes.

Despite these contributions, the study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the training data is primarily drawn from computer science disciplines, which may constrain the immediate generalisability of the model to other academic domains such as medicine, law, and humanities. Second, the qualitative component relied on data from 10 of the 13 identified Tanzanian universities, which may introduce selection bias. Third, the evaluation was conducted within a single

national context (Tanzania), limiting direct applicability to other educational systems without adaptation. Fourth, the model's performance is bounded by the quality and representativeness of the OER and examination data used for fine-tuning.

Future research should address these limitations through several directions. First, the dataset should be extended beyond computer science to include humanities, health sciences, and engineering curricula, thereby improving cross-disciplinary generalisability. Second, the framework should be validated across other East African and broader African university systems to assess its adaptability to diverse regulatory and linguistic contexts. Third, future studies should explore the integration of larger PLM architectures (e.g., BERT-large, RoBERTa) as computational resources permit and investigate multilingual models to accommodate Swahili-medium instruction. Fourth, the development of a standardised curricular ontology would substantially enhance feature alignment and semantic benchmarking capabilities. Finally, real-time deployment studies with university quality assurance offices are recommended to evaluate the framework's usability and impact in practice.

5 Disclosure

5.1 Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated and/or analysed during this study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

5.2 Details of Ethical Clearance

The research protocol was approved by the School of Computational and Communication Science and Engineering (CoCSE), Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST), Tanzania, in accordance with institutional research guidelines. Data collection was conducted with permission from ten higher learning institutions in Tanzania: Mwenge Catholic University, Arusha Technical College, University of Dar es Salaam, University of Dodoma, Mbeya University of Science and Technology, Institute of Finance Management (IFM), Jordan University College, Kampala International University, St. Joseph University College of Engineering and Technology, Ruaha Catholic University, and the National Institute of Transport. Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

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5.4 Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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